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“SO MANY STARS THAT YELL ABOVE AND NONE IS SEEN”¹

MALANDRA COURT AND THE SYMBOLIC REPRESENTATION OF URBAN VIOLENCE IN VENEZUELA

ABSTRACT

Urban violence enters into, and creates interstices in both public and private life of Venezuelans and, as revealed by academic studies to the mass media, has made Caracas one of the most chaotic and unsafe cities in the world by the number of murders, robberies, and kidnappings, with latent cultural anxiety (Martin-Barbero), in which the majority of its inhabitants lives. Hence that is drawn around an imaginary, in some cases established by their own players. In this paper, we will seek an approach to urban violence, emphasizing the dynamics of new forms of representation, and the emergence of alternative discourses of hegemony, which set up a fresh look on it.

KEY WORDS

Malandra court, urban violence representations, Venezuela.

*Oh, Hail queen, María Lionza
over Venezuela she goes with her ounce taking care of it
looking after its entire land
(...)*

¹ The phrase appearing as the title of this paper was taken from the short story ‘El frío’, de *Salsa y control* (1996), written by José Roberto Duque. J.R. Duque, ‘El frío’ in idem, *Salsa y control*, Caracas 1996.